

Translation of Outdoor Signs in Nusa Dua Beach Area

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ABSTRACT: This research was conducted to have a closer look at Linguistic Landscape in one of coastal areas of Bali, Indonesia. It specifically conducted with the aim of analyzing the translation of outdoor signs, in the form of notice or information boards. This research also examines translation shifts occur within those outdoor signs.

This research is a qualitative descriptive study. The method applied for this research is observation method and include image capture and also note-taking technique. The problem formulated in this research applies Linguistic Landscape theory by Landry and Bourhis and also Translation Shift theory by Catford and Simatupang.

The result of the research found that the form of translation of the outdoor signs in Nusa Dua beach area can be seen in the form of Notice board, cemented sign, or colored banner which has function to give information or warning to the people who visit the area. It also can be found that the shift occurs in the translation of the outdoor signs consists of structure and meaning shift.

KEYWORDS: Linguistic Landscape, Nusa Dua Beach, Outdoor signs, Translation Shift, Translation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation can be defined as a process and a product. The definition of process shows that translation places more emphasis on how a translator processes the text in writing or orally. Meanwhile, in terms of product definition, translation is seen more from the aspect of the results.

There are various definitions regarding translation from experts. Hatim & Mason (2004:26) state that translation is an activity that can clearly prove the role of language in social life. Newmark (1981:27) defines translation as the process of transferring the meaning of a series or linguistic unit, of the whole or part of a text from one language to another. Meanwhile, Larson (1984:3) states that translation is the transfer of meaning from the source language to the target language. Larson also defines translation more broadly, it stated that translating is an activity that consists of three things: a) researching the lexicon, communication situation, grammatical structure and cultural context in the source language; b) analysing the source language text to find its meaning; and c) re-express the same meaning using lexicon and grammatical structures appropriate to the target language. Catford (1965: 20) believes that translation is the transfer of text from the source language to the equivalent text in the target language.

Translation of linguistic landscape in outdoor signs is significant and interesting to be discussed due to the reason that we can examine how language is applied in public spaces, it can help people to understand information conveyed through its written form. Outdoor signs can include various signs, the focus on in this research is outdoor written signs of bilingual announcement boards located in Nusa Dua beach area.

There are ample of studies regarding Translation and Linguistic Landscape. Beili & Tuo (2015) analyzed Chinese and English translations in the linguistic landscape of China. Data is collected from several sources, such as airports, supermarkets, bus stations, tourist attractions, and so on. This research applies descriptive and exploratory methods. The research results show that translation errors occur, such as syntactic, lexical, pragmatic and semantic errors, which are caused by two key factors, they are government negligence and translators who are not yet proficient in carrying out their duties. This omission affects the accuracy of the information received by the reader of the sign. Therefore, researchers propose several translation techniques so that the results are more in line with the target language (TL), including: borrowing, addition and omission techniques. Apart from that, it is also recommended that government policies and attitudes towards the results of translating signs in a place be given more attention to avoid such mistakes being repeated.

Shi (2020) also conducted a study on the translation of universally used public signs in Chinese and English. This study is motivated by the idea that as China's internationalization increases, pragmatic failure is becoming a common problem in cross-cultural communication on public signs. Different languages bring different pragmatic rules and constraints, so that a pragmatic perspective

can be used to analyze pragmatic failures in the translation of public signs, as well as appropriate translation strategies to promote harmony between mother tongue and target language expressions. This harmony of expression is important in cross-cultural communication in order to avoid communication conflicts and bring linguistic comfort to public signs.

Puspani, et al., (2021) researched sign posts in Nusa Penida by applying the theory of Ben-Rafael et.al., (2006), and Landry & Bourhis (1997) that a sign shapes language conditions in the environment. This study tests Gorter's (2012) assumption that monolingual signboards are rarely found in tourism areas. The results of the research show that some of the direction signs in the Nusa Penida tourism area have more than one language (multilingual), they include Balinese, Indonesian and English, which reflects the desire of the people of Nusa Penida to provide good tourism services, as well as showing loyalty. on local identity as Balinese people.

Based on the brief introduction and the previous researches, this research tries to answer the following formulated questions, such as:

- (1) the form of translation of outdoor signs in Nusa Dua beach area
- (2) the translation shift of outdoor signs found in Nusa Dua beach area

The results of this research are expected to have theoretical and practical benefits. The theoretical benefit aims to broaden the reader's insight, concerning Translation and also Linguistic landscape. This research is also expected to be able to give insight practically to the local government and tourism practitioner of Nusa Dua beach area.

METHOD

This research is field research with observation method and applying image capture and note taking technique. The data collected by finding out the outdoor signs in coastal area of Nusa Dua beach. The data later being classified and analyzed based on the theory applied. The theory applied for this research is the Linguistic Landscape theory, Translation theory and also supported by translation shift theory.

Landry & Bourhis (1997:25) shows that the strong relation among community, space, and language. It states that the most basic informational function of the linguistic landscape is that it serves as a distinct marker of the geographical territory inhabited by a given language community, [...] inform[ing] in-group and out-group members of the linguistic characteristics, territorial limits, and language boundaries of the region where they have entered.

The meaning that can be understood from this statement is that LL has an important function to inform the linguistic status of a community that inhabits a certain area, as well as informing other communities or groups that enter that area that they are in a different geographical area and linguistic landscape. Furthermore, Landry & Bourhis (1997:25) also emphasized that writing in LL is a symbolic marker that shows community relationships with their relative power and status. Thus, LL has two main functions, an informative function and a symbolic function.

Translation can be defined in various ways. In simple terms, translation is the process of transferring a message from the source language to the target language. Newmark (1988:27) defines translation as the process of transferring the meaning of a series or linguistic unit, of the whole or part of a text from one language to another. Meanwhile, Larson (1984:1) defines translation more broadly, that translating is an activity that consists of three things: a) researching the lexicon, communication situation, grammatical structure and cultural context in the source language; b) analyzing the source language text to find its meaning; and c) re-express the same meaning using lexicon and grammatical structures appropriate to the target language.

Catford (1978:73) states that the form of shifts can be classified into two types, they are level shifts and category shifts with the following explanation.

Level shift means that words that are at one level in the SL have their equivalents at a different level in the TL. Each linguistic system (phonology, morphology, syntax) consists of units that form a scale of levels, namely from the smallest level to the largest level. In English grammar, for example, there are sentence units, clauses, phrases, words and morphemes, each of which has certain grammatical behaviour. A sentence consisting of one or more clauses is a higher unit than a clause. Then, a clause consisting of several groups of words (phrases) is a higher unit than a phrase. Likewise, phrases are higher units than words, such as 'daughter' in English which is translated as "*anak perempuan*" in Indonesian is a phrase.

According to Catford (1978:75-80), category shifts can be divided into four categories, as follows: (1) structure shifts are shifts in the order of translation in the TL; (2) word class shift is a shift in items in translation, such as a shift from noun to adjective, noun

to verb shift, and adjective to noun shift; (3) unit shift is a shift at the translation level, for example from words to phrases, then from phrases to clauses, and from clauses to sentences; and (4) intra-system shift is a shift that occurs due to different grammatical rules, for example, in SL a word has an article, but in SL it does not, and the concept of pluralism becomes a certain word.

Apart from form shifts, in translation, meaning shifts often occur or are often called semantic shifts. According to Simatupang (2000:92), a shift in meaning or semantics is a shift that occurs due to differences in viewpoints and cultures of speakers of different languages. Shifting meaning is a necessity because it is not always possible to transfer the meaning of source language (TL) into the text or target language (TL) precisely or completely.

The locus of the research is Nusa Dua area. Nusa Dua beach is one of the well-known coastal areas in Bali, it was chosen because historically Nusa Dua is an area that first established by SCETO, France in 1972 to provide a specific and elite area for tourists. There is no research yet available in this locus particularly about linguistic landscape of outdoor signs and translation. Thus, this leads to the new value of the research because it is not only exploring how language used in public space, particularly in coastal well-known area but it also may serve as feedback to local government of how the outdoor signs should be presented. The collected data is analyzed by applying framework of Linguistic Landscape by Laundry and Borhuis and also Theory of Translation by Catford supported by Simatupang. The result of the research is presented in informal method and written descriptively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research tries to reveal and see the language position; how it applies in public spaces. The urgency to have this research due to the fact that there has no research yet in Nusa Dua area concerning Linguistic Landscape (LL) and Translation. Having a closer look at LL in the coastal area enable readers to see dynamic usage of language; it serves the function not only to give information, awareness, warning and others, but it also give us further understanding of how language and the translation is presented in outdoor signs of public spaces.

In this section, there are four outdoor signs analyzed to find out the form of the translation and also to find the shifts occur. Those outdoor signs are the representation of all outdoor signs found in the mentioned area. The discussion is presented in brief description and elucidated with the theories applied.

A. *Form of translation of outdoor signs in Nusa Dua beach area*

This subchapter present outdoor signs found in Nusa Dua beach area. The outdoor signs presented in various forms such as in notice board, banner, evacuation route sign, and cemented outdoor signs. Those outdoor signs are presented in the following figures:

Figure 1

The form of translation of outdoor sign in Nusa Dua beach area found in Figure 1 is written in a white colored notice board with black capital writing. It is presented in bilingual form of Indonesian language and English Translation.

Figure 2

The form of translation of outdoor sign in Nusa dua beach area shown in Figure 2 is written in a red banner with yellow capital writing and placed in a wired fence near the beach. The language used is Indonesian language in the top part and English translation below, with triple exclamation mark in the word 'Perhatian-Attention'.

Figure 3

The form of translation of outdoor sign above shown in Figure 3 shows direction of evacuation route. Presented in green arrow shaped board, the sign written in white colored writing. In the right side of the sign, we can see a picture of a running man. Unlike figure 1 and 2, this figure features condense phrase in Indonesian and English version.

Figure 4

The form of translation of outdoor signs shown in above Figure, Figure 4 shows warning sign, presented in a cemented white colored sign with gold writing. There are 7 information regarding the warning featured, particularly about dangerous things that visitors need to be aware of, such as the wave, the coral, the surf and others.

B. The translation shift of outdoor signs found in Nusa Dua beach area

Figure 1

SL :

PERHATIAN

MANDILAH SELALU DIANTARA DUA BENDERA MERAH KUNING

TL :

NOTICE

ALWAYS SWIM BETWEEN TWO RED YELLOW FLAGS

The above figure shows a notice board in Nusa Dua beach area. The announcement is displayed in two languages, Indonesian and English. Indonesian is applied as the Source Language (SL) and English is the Target Language (TL). The use of bilingual in the outdoor sign above has an important role in conveying important messages or information regarding restrictions on swimming in coastal areas for domestic and foreign tourists.

The lexical '*PERHATIAN*' is translated into '*NOTICE*' in Target Language. It includes in meaning shift because literally the word '*perhatian*' can be translated into '*attention*' in English. However, the lexical stated in the board shows different meaning, it does not refer to attention but it refers to notice; paying attention to something.

The shift that can be found from the above data can be seen at the level of the phrase '*Mandilah selalu*' which is translated into '*always swim*'. This phrase experienced a category shift, which is structure shift.

The verb '*mandi*' followed by suffix *-lah* and accompanied by the adverb '*always*' is translated into an adverb-verb. From the data, it is also found that there is a shift in the lexical meaning of the word '*mandi*' in SL to the word '*swim*' in TL. These two words have different meanings, but the notice board showed because it is considered to be equivalent in terms of the context of the situation in which the board is placed. There is also a shift in the lost of information; suffix '*-lah*' is not translated in SL.

The lexical '*mandi*' is translated into '*swim*' in the TL. The word '*mandi*' is usually translated as '*bath*' or '*shower*' in English. According to Cambridge Dictionary, the word '*bath*' itself is defined as an act of washing in a bath (verb), a large container holding water in which to wash the whole body, a container of liquid (noun). Therefore, the phrase shows shift in meaning. There is a strong difference between the lexical '*mandi*' and '*swim*' seen from cultural context of Indonesian and English. Both lexical has involved activity or using element of water. However, practically, the execution is conducted differently. Indonesian will relate '*mandi*' because it involves water, applying soap and can be done by shower with '*gayung*' or soaking in a bathtub. The word '*mandi*' itself can also refers to a more comprehensive activity if the adverbial place is mentioned; for instance, '*mandi di sungai*' (taking a bath in the river).

In the other hand, '*to swim*' is a sport activity which is not equal to '*mandi*'. Lexically the word '*swim*' defines as to move through water using arms, and legs, or fins, tail, etc (verb), to cross (a river etc, to compete in (a race), to cover (a distance etc) by swimming and it can also define as to seem to be moving round and round as a result of dizziness.

Figure 2

SL :

PERHATIAN!!!

DEMI KEAMANAN,

PARKIRLAH KENDARAAN ANDA DI TEMPAT YANG SUDAH DISEDIAKAN.

TL :

ATTENTION!!!

PARK YOUR VEHICLE IN THE PARKING LOT FOR YOUR SAFETY

The above figure shows there are shifts occurs within the outdoor signs which presented in the red banner. The outdoor sign features similar data from figure 1, however, the translation is different. The lexical '*Perhatian!!!*' in SL is translated into 'Attention' in TL. According to Cambridge dictionary, the translation of '*Perhatian*' (noun) is equal to 'Attention' (noun) in TL; showing that the translation is a literal translation.

In the following analysis, there is shift occurrence in the loss of phrase '*DEMI KEAMANAN*' in TL. The phrase does not show in TL; the shift shows the loss of information.

The following phrase of '*DI TEMPAT YANG SUDAH DISEDIAKAN*' is translated into 'IN THE PARKING LOT' in TL. The shift occurs is included as category shift, in particular the structure shift. The SL consists of preposition '*di*' and then followed by Noun '*tempat*' and also followed by Clause '*yang sudah disediakan*'. Meanwhile the TL includes Preposition 'in' followed by article 'the' and also Noun Phrase of 'Parking Lot'. There is also shift of additional information of phrase 'Your Safety' which is not shown in the SL. the obvious difference of the shift is in the use of article 'the' in TL and also the change of word class Clause of SL which translated into Noun Phrase (NP) in the TL.

Figure 3

SL : JALUR EVAKUASI

TL : EVACUATION ROUTE

The outdoor sign above shows information sign regarding the evacuation route of the beach. In western culture, safety induction is a significant matter to be acknowledged by workers or common people in public spaces because safety is priority. As we see in figure 3, the outdoor sign points and give direction where people should go in case emergency occurs.

The data shows meaning shift. In SL '*jalur*' according to KBBI (Indonesian dictionary) defines as '*ruang*' and can be translated into 'track' in TL. In the above data we can see that it is translated into 'route' in TL. The word 'route' itself is defined as distance that need to be taken. The gap of 'space' and 'distance' is clearly seen in the above phrase. In native English, the phrase 'evacuation route' is acceptable in the community instead of 'evacuation track'

Figure 4

The above figure shows some information regarding caution to visit the beach. This sign found in Water Blow beach of Nusa Dua. The translation shift can be found in the following text or phrase (a) 'Perhatian, (b) Ombak berbahaya, (c) 'Tebing curam'

(a) ST : *Perhatian*

TT : Caution

The shift occurs of the above text is included as meaning shift. The word '*Perhatian*' in the ST is translated into 'Caution' in the TT. According to online dictionary of KBBI the word '*Perhatian*' is defined as '*mengalihkan perhatian* or distract (English) and commonly translated into 'attention' in the TT. The word 'Caution' in Indonesian equivalent into '*Peringatan*' which is rather different from the word '*Perhatian*'.

(b) ST : *Ombak berbahaya*

TT : Dangerous shorebreak

The (b) data shows the shift of meaning from general to specific. The ST phrase of '*Ombak berbahaya*' is translated into '*Dangerous shorebreak*' in TT. Shorebreak is defined as waves which quickly peak and break onshore to a relatively sharply sloping beach. This term is usually use among surfers. The common translation of ST is 'dangerous waves'. The lexical 'wave' is commonly understood by many people.

(c) ST : *Tebing curam*

TT : Sudden drop off

The figure 4c is not included in any kind of shift because the translation is not correct. The ST of '*Tebing curam*' should be translated into 'Steep cliff'. However, the sign shows the translation of TT is 'Sudden drof off'. It is eventually can be considered as the result of a steep cliff when you accidentally fall down of a cliff.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above discussion, it can be found that the form of translation of the outdoor signs in Nusa Dua beach area can be seen in the form of Notice board, cemented sign, or coloured banner which has function to give information or warning to the people who visit the area. The lexical '*Perhatian*' can be translated into three different lexicals as they have been discussed in the above discussion. They are translated into 'Notice', 'Attention', and 'Caution'. The lexical variations shows the nature of translation, which is to re-express the same meaning using lexicon and grammatical structures appropriate to the target language.

The research also found that the shift occurs in the translation of the outdoor signs consists of structure and meaning shift. The result of the discussion also show that the structure shift occurs because of the different structure of ST to TT, and the meaning shift occur due to cultural differences of both languages.

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